

Duetti per clarinetti

Op. 10

Diego Casadei

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Dialogo 2

Egiziana

Diego Casadei

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♩ = 136

Musical score for measures 1-4. The piece is in 2/4 time with a key signature of one sharp (F#). The tempo is marked as ♩ = 136. The first staff (treble clef) begins with a piano (*p*) dynamic and features a continuous eighth-note triplet pattern. The second staff (treble clef) is mostly silent, with a piano (*p*) dynamic marking at the start of measure 4. The bass staff (bass clef) enters in measure 4 with a piano (*p*) dynamic and a triplet pattern, marked with a *cresc.* (crescendo) instruction.

Musical score for measures 5-8. The first staff (treble clef) continues the eighth-note triplet pattern, marked with a *leggero* instruction. The second staff (treble clef) remains silent. The bass staff (bass clef) continues its triplet pattern, also marked with a *leggero* instruction.

Musical score for measures 9-12. The first staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with eighth-note triplets and a *b* (flat) marking above the staff in measure 10. The second staff (treble clef) continues the eighth-note triplet pattern. The bass staff (bass clef) continues the eighth-note triplet pattern.

Musical score for measures 13-16. The first staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with eighth-note triplets and a *cresc.* (crescendo) instruction. The second staff (treble clef) continues the eighth-note triplet pattern. The bass staff (bass clef) continues the eighth-note triplet pattern, marked with a *mf* (mezzo-forte) dynamic.

27

f

21

subito p

25

cresc. cresc.

29

f

33

ff

11

Musical notation for measures 11-12. The top staff features a melodic line with a slur and a fermata. The bottom staff contains a complex rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, heavily utilizing triplets.

13

Musical notation for measures 13-14. The top staff continues the rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with triplets. The bottom staff features a melodic line with a slur and a fermata.

15

Musical notation for measures 15-16. The top staff continues the rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with triplets. The bottom staff features a melodic line with a slur and a fermata.

17

Musical notation for measures 17-18. The top staff continues the rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with triplets. The bottom staff features a melodic line with a slur and a fermata.

19

Musical notation for measures 19-20. The top staff continues the rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with triplets. The bottom staff features a melodic line with a slur and a fermata. Dynamics *p* are indicated.

21

Musical notation for measures 21-22. The top staff continues the rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with triplets. The bottom staff features a melodic line with a slur and a fermata. Dynamics *dim.* are indicated.

Dialogo 4

Clementina

Diego Casadei

Musical notation for measures 1-6. The score is in 2/4 time with a key signature of one sharp (F#). The upper staff begins with a *mp* dynamic and a *cresc.* marking. The lower staff begins with a *mp* dynamic. The music features a melodic line in the upper staff and a supporting bass line in the lower staff.

Musical notation for measures 7-11. The upper staff continues with a melodic line, and the lower staff provides a bass line. The dynamics and markings from the previous system are maintained.

Musical notation for measures 12-17. The upper staff features a melodic line with some rests, and the lower staff provides a bass line. The dynamics and markings from the previous system are maintained.

Musical notation for measures 18-23. The upper staff begins with a *mf* dynamic. The lower staff also begins with a *mf* dynamic. The music features a melodic line in the upper staff and a supporting bass line in the lower staff.

Musical notation for measures 24-29. The upper staff begins with a *cresc.* marking. The lower staff also begins with a *cresc.* marking. The music features a melodic line in the upper staff and a supporting bass line in the lower staff.

29

mp *cresc.*

mp *cresc.*

35

cresc.

subito mp cresc.

41

subito mp cresc.

subito mp cresc.

46

ff

ff

52

ff

Dialogo 5

Mozartiana

Diego Casadei

Measures 1-6 of the piece. The music is in 2/4 time with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). Both staves begin with a piano (*p*) dynamic. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and grace notes, while the lower staff provides a rhythmic accompaniment.

Measures 7-12. Measure 7 is marked with a *cresc.* (crescendo) dynamic. The upper staff has a melodic line with slurs and grace notes, and the lower staff has a rhythmic accompaniment. Measure 12 ends with a *dim.* (diminuendo) dynamic.

Measures 13-18. Measure 13 is marked with a piano (*p*) dynamic. Measure 14 is marked with a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic. The upper staff has a melodic line with slurs and grace notes, and the lower staff has a rhythmic accompaniment.

Measures 19-24. Measure 19 is marked with a piano (*p*) dynamic. Measure 24 is marked with a *leggero* dynamic. The upper staff has a melodic line with slurs and grace notes, and the lower staff has a rhythmic accompaniment.

Measures 25-30. The upper staff has a melodic line with slurs and grace notes, and the lower staff has a rhythmic accompaniment.

31

Musical notation for measures 31-36. The top staff features a melodic line with a long slur and a trill. The bottom staff features a rhythmic accompaniment of eighth notes.

37

Musical notation for measures 37-42. The top staff has dynamics *cresc.* and *dim.*. The bottom staff has dynamics *cresc.* and *dim.*.

43

Musical notation for measures 43-48. The top staff has dynamics *cresc.* and *dim.*. The bottom staff has dynamics *cresc.* and *dim.*.

49

Musical notation for measures 49-54. The top staff has a dynamic *p*. The bottom staff has a dynamic *p*.

Dialogo 7

à la Maurice

Diego Casadei

Lento $\text{♩} = 72$

p sempre

p sempre

9

9

18

18

27

27

mp

p

35

Musical score for measures 35-42. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef and a key signature of one flat. It contains a melodic line with various note values, including eighth and sixteenth notes, and rests. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and contains a corresponding bass line. Dynamic markings include *p* and *pp*. There are also hairpins indicating crescendos and decrescendos.

43

Musical score for measures 43-50. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line from the previous system. The lower staff continues the bass line. Dynamic markings include *p* and *pp*. There are also hairpins indicating crescendos and decrescendos.

51

Musical score for measures 51-59. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with a *p sempre* marking. The lower staff features a bass line with a *p sempre* marking. The music is characterized by a consistent rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.

60

Musical score for measures 60-67. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with a *pp* marking. The lower staff features a bass line with a *pp* marking. The music concludes with a double bar line.

Dialogo 12

Cavalliniana

Diego Casadei

mf *p*

mf *f*

p *cresc.*

p *dim.*

mf *mf*

27

f

33

mp

39

cresc.

f cresc.

45

ff

mp

50

ff

mp

p

56 *mf* *p*

61 *f* *f*

66 *p* *cresc.* *p*

70 *sempre f* *sempre f*

74

Dialogo 1

Romantico

Diego Casadei

♩ = 60

p *sempre*

p

11

mp *mp* *p* *cresc.*

mp *p* *cresc.*

21

p *cresc.* *mp*

p *cresc.* *mp*

31

f *f*

39

pp *sempre*

pp *sempre*

Dialogo 9

Bachiana

Diego Casadei

Musical notation for measures 1-7. The piece is in 2/4 time with a key signature of one sharp (F#). The first staff (treble clef) has rests for the first four measures, followed by eighth-note patterns in measures 5-7. The second staff (bass clef) features a continuous eighth-note accompaniment throughout.

Musical notation for measures 8-14. Measure 8 is marked with a '8'. The first staff (treble clef) contains sixteenth-note runs, while the second staff (bass clef) continues with eighth-note accompaniment.

Musical notation for measures 15-21. Measure 15 is marked with a '15'. The first staff (treble clef) features sixteenth-note runs, and the second staff (bass clef) continues with eighth-note accompaniment.

Musical notation for measures 22-28. Measure 22 is marked with a '22'. The first staff (treble clef) contains sixteenth-note runs, and the second staff (bass clef) continues with eighth-note accompaniment.

Musical notation for measures 29-35. Measure 29 is marked with a '29'. The first staff (treble clef) contains sixteenth-note runs, and the second staff (bass clef) continues with eighth-note accompaniment.

36

Musical score for measures 36-42. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. Both are in the key of D major. The music features a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth and thirty-second notes, often beamed together. There are several rests in the upper staff, particularly in measures 37, 38, and 39.

43

Musical score for measures 43-49. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. Both are in the key of D major. The music continues with intricate rhythmic patterns, including many sixteenth and thirty-second notes. There are several rests in the upper staff, particularly in measures 44, 45, and 46.

50

Musical score for measures 50-56. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. Both are in the key of D major. The music features a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth and thirty-second notes, often beamed together. There are several rests in the upper staff, particularly in measures 51, 52, and 53.

57

Musical score for measures 57-63. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. Both are in the key of D major. The music features a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth and thirty-second notes, often beamed together. There are several rests in the upper staff, particularly in measures 58, 59, and 60.

64

Musical score for measures 64-70. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. Both are in the key of D major. The music features a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth and thirty-second notes, often beamed together. There are several rests in the upper staff, particularly in measures 65, 66, and 67.

Dialogo 10

Modernamente

Diego Casadei

Musical notation for measures 1-7. The score is in 4/4 time and B-flat major. The upper staff begins with a piano (*pp*) dynamic, followed by a crescendo to fortissimo (*ff*), and then returns to piano (*pp*). The lower staff contains a series of chords and rests.

Musical notation for measures 8-10. The upper staff features a melodic line starting with a piano (*mf*) dynamic and a crescendo. The lower staff has a bass line with rests and a final note in measure 10.

Musical notation for measures 11-13. The upper staff continues the melodic line with a fortissimo (*f*) dynamic. The lower staff has a bass line with rests and a melodic phrase in measure 13.

Musical notation for measures 14-16. The upper staff features a melodic line with triplets and a fortissimo (*f*) dynamic. The lower staff has a bass line with rests and a melodic phrase in measure 16.

Musical notation for measures 17-19. The upper staff features a melodic line with a piano (*p*) dynamic. The lower staff has a bass line with rests and a melodic phrase in measure 19.

20

p

p

Musical notation for measures 20-21. The top staff features a complex melodic line with many beamed sixteenth notes and slurs. The bottom staff provides a rhythmic accompaniment with similar beamed notes. Both staves are marked with a piano (*p*) dynamic.

22

mf

mf

Musical notation for measures 22-23. The top staff has a melodic line with slurs and a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic. The bottom staff continues the accompaniment with a similar *mf* dynamic.

24

mf

mf

Musical notation for measures 24-25. The top staff includes a triplet of sixteenth notes. The bottom staff features a steady accompaniment. Both staves are marked with a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic.

28

mf

f

mf

f

Musical notation for measures 28-29. The top staff shows a melodic line with slurs, marked with *mf* and *f*. The bottom staff has a rhythmic accompaniment, also marked with *mf* and *f*.

31

ff subito *p*

ff subito *p*

subito p

subito p

Musical notation for measures 31-35. The top staff consists of chords, marked with *ff* subito *p* and *subito p*. The bottom staff has a simple accompaniment of chords, also marked with *ff* subito *p* and *subito p*.

Dialogo 8

Danse macabre Diego Casadei (after C. Saint-Saens)

Musical notation for measures 1-8. The piece is in 3/4 time with a key signature of one sharp (F#). Both the upper and lower staves begin with a forte (*f*) dynamic. The upper staff features a melodic line of quarter notes, while the lower staff provides a rhythmic accompaniment of eighth notes.

Musical notation for measures 9-14. The upper staff starts with a piano (*p*) dynamic and includes a *V* (accents) and a *tr* (trill) marking. The lower staff also begins with a piano (*p*) dynamic and features a *V* marking. The melodic line in the upper staff continues with eighth notes and trills.

Musical notation for measures 15-20. The upper staff includes a *tr* marking and a *V* marking. The lower staff features a *V* marking and a *tr* marking. The melodic line in the upper staff continues with eighth notes and trills.

Musical notation for measures 21-27. The upper staff includes a *cresc.* (crescendo) marking. The lower staff includes a *tr* marking and a *cresc.* marking. The melodic line in the upper staff continues with eighth notes and trills.

Musical notation for measures 28-33. The upper staff includes a *f* (forte) dynamic marking. The lower staff includes a *f* dynamic marking. The melodic line in the upper staff continues with eighth notes and trills.

36

36

p V D

p V

Detailed description: This system contains measures 36 through 41. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and ties, marked with a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 40. The lower staff provides a harmonic accompaniment with a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 40. The key signature has two sharps (F# and C#).

42

42

S *tr* D V *cresc.*

cresc. V

Detailed description: This system contains measures 42 through 47. The upper staff includes slurs, ties, and a trill (*tr*) in measure 43, marked with a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 45. The lower staff has a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 45. The key signature has two sharps (F# and C#).

48

48

V D *p* *S* *tr* D V *cresc.*

p V *cresc.*

Detailed description: This system contains measures 48 through 53. The upper staff features slurs, ties, and a trill (*tr*) in measure 51, marked with a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 53. The lower staff has a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 53. The key signature has two sharps (F# and C#).

54

54

cresc. V

cresc.

Detailed description: This system contains measures 54 through 61. The upper staff has a melodic line with a crescendo (*cresc.*) and a breath mark (V) above measure 61. The lower staff has a piano (*p*) dynamic and a breath mark (V) above measure 61. The key signature has two sharps (F# and C#).

62

62

f *tr* *tr*

f

Detailed description: This system contains measures 62 through 67. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and ties, marked with a forte (*f*) dynamic and trills (*tr*) in measures 65 and 66. The lower staff has a forte (*f*) dynamic. The key signature has two sharps (F# and C#).

68

Musical notation for measures 68-73. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one sharp (F#), and a common time signature. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a trill (tr) and a fermata. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. It contains six measures of music, with a fermata in the first measure. A 'V' marking is present above the second measure of the lower staff.

74

Musical notation for measures 74-79. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one sharp, and a common time signature. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a trill (tr) and a fermata. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a trill (tr) and a fermata. A 'V' marking is present above the fourth measure of the upper staff.

80

Musical notation for measures 80-86. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one sharp, and a common time signature. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a trill (tr) and a fermata. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a trill (tr) and a fermata. A 'V' marking is present above the fifth measure of the lower staff, which is also marked with a mezzo-forte (mf) dynamic.

87

Musical notation for measures 87-93. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one sharp, and a common time signature. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a mezzo-forte (mf) dynamic. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a fermata. A 'cresc.' marking is present above the second measure of the upper staff, and another 'cresc.' marking is present below the second measure of the lower staff.

94

Musical notation for measures 94-99. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one sharp, and a common time signature. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a forte (f) dynamic. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. It contains six measures of music, with the first measure marked with a forte (f) dynamic. A 'p' marking is present above the third measure of the upper staff, and another 'p' marking is present above the fourth measure of the lower staff. A 'f' marking is present above the fifth measure of the upper staff, and another 'f' marking is present above the sixth measure of the lower staff.

Dialogo 11

Minimalista

Diego Casadei

The first system of music consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#) and a common time signature (C). It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, some with accents (>). The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature and time signature, and contains whole rests.

The second system of music consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line from the first system. The lower staff has a '5' written above the first measure and contains whole rests.

The third system of music consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line. The lower staff has a '10' written above the first measure and contains whole rests.

The fourth system of music consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line. The lower staff has a '15' written above the first measure and contains whole rests.

The fifth system of music consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line. The lower staff has a '20' written above the first measure and contains whole rests.

25

Musical notation for measures 25-29. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#), and a common time signature. It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The lower staff begins with a treble clef and the same key signature, containing a bass line with eighth and sixteenth notes, also featuring accents and slurs.

30

Musical notation for measures 30-34. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line from the previous system. The lower staff continues the bass line, showing a change in the bass clef staff's key signature to one sharp (F#) in measure 33.

35

Musical notation for measures 35-39. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line. The lower staff continues the bass line, maintaining the one sharp key signature.

40

Musical notation for measures 40-44. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line. The lower staff continues the bass line.

45

Musical notation for measures 45-49. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line. The lower staff continues the bass line, ending with a key signature change to one flat (F) in measure 49.

50

Musical notation for measures 50-53. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#), and a common time signature. It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and contains a bass line with eighth and sixteenth notes, also featuring accents and slurs.

54

Musical notation for measures 54-57. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps, and a common time signature. It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and contains a bass line with eighth and sixteenth notes, also featuring accents and slurs.

58

Musical notation for measures 58-62. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps, and a common time signature. It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and contains a bass line with eighth and sixteenth notes, also featuring accents and slurs.

63

Musical notation for measures 63-67. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps, and a common time signature. It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and contains a bass line with eighth and sixteenth notes, also featuring accents and slurs.

68

Musical notation for measures 68-71. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps, and a common time signature. It contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The lower staff begins with a bass clef and contains a bass line with eighth and sixteenth notes, also featuring accents and slurs.

La Cumparsita

Diego Casadei (after G. M. Rodríguez)

Tango (♩ = c. 120)

Musical score for B♭ Clarinet, consisting of five systems of two staves each. The music is in common time (C) and features a variety of dynamics and articulations. The first system (measures 1-5) starts with a forte (*f*) dynamic in the upper staff and a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic in the lower staff. The second system (measures 6-11) continues with *mf* dynamics. The third system (measures 12-17) features a forte (*f*) dynamic. The fourth system (measures 18-24) is marked mezzo-piano (*mp*). The fifth system (measures 25-30) also features a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. The score includes numerous triplet markings (indicated by a '3' above the notes) and accents (indicated by a 'v' symbol below the notes). The piece concludes with a sharp sign (♯) at the end of the fifth system.

31

31

f *f*

f *mf*

3

Detailed description: This system contains measures 31 through 36. The upper staff begins with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). It features a melodic line with a repeat sign at measure 34. The lower staff starts with a bass clef and contains a rhythmic accompaniment with several triplet markings. Dynamic markings include *f* (forte) and *mf* (mezzo-forte).

37

37

3

Detailed description: This system contains measures 37 through 41. The upper staff continues the melodic line with various ornaments and slurs. The lower staff continues the rhythmic accompaniment with triplet markings. The key signature remains one sharp.

42

42

p *mp*

3

Detailed description: This system contains measures 42 through 47. The upper staff begins with a piano (*p*) dynamic and features a melodic line with slurs. The lower staff continues the accompaniment with triplet markings and a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. The key signature remains one sharp.

48

48

f *mf* *mp*

3

Detailed description: This system contains measures 48 through 53. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic. The lower staff continues the accompaniment with triplet markings and a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. The key signature remains one sharp.

54

54

mf *f* *mf*

3

Detailed description: This system contains measures 54 through 59. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic. The lower staff continues the accompaniment with triplet markings and a forte (*f*) dynamic. The key signature remains one sharp.

60

Musical notation for measures 60-65. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff contains a melodic line with slurs and accents. The lower staff contains a bass line with triplets and slurs. Dynamics include *f* (forte) and *mf* (mezzo-forte).

66

Musical notation for measures 66-70. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents, alternating between *f* and *p* dynamics. The lower staff features a bass line with slurs and accents, alternating between *f* and *p* dynamics.

71

Musical notation for measures 71-75. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents, alternating between *p* and *f* dynamics. The lower staff features a bass line with slurs and accents, alternating between *f* and *p* dynamics. Dynamics include *p*, *f*, *mp*, and *mf*.

76

Musical notation for measures 76-82. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents, including triplets. The lower staff features a bass line with slurs and accents, including triplets. Dynamics include *f* and *mf*.

83

Musical notation for measures 83-88. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents, including a long note. The lower staff features a bass line with slurs and accents, including triplets. Dynamics include *mf* and *mp*.

86

mp

mf

Detailed description: This system contains measures 86, 87, and 88. The top staff begins with a treble clef and a whole note G4. The bottom staff begins with a treble clef and a whole note G3. Both staves feature a crescendo hairpin starting at measure 86. The music consists of eighth-note patterns with slurs and ties. Dynamic markings include *mp* (mezzo-piano) and *mf* (mezzo-forte).

89

Detailed description: This system contains measures 89, 90, and 91. The top staff continues with eighth-note patterns. The bottom staff features a whole note G3 in measure 89, followed by quarter notes in measures 90 and 91. The music concludes with a decrescendo hairpin.

92

mf

mp

Detailed description: This system contains measures 92, 93, and 94. The top staff has a whole note G4 in measure 92, followed by quarter notes. The bottom staff has quarter notes in measure 92, followed by eighth-note patterns in measures 93 and 94. Dynamic markings include *mf* and *mp*.

95

f

f

Detailed description: This system contains measures 95, 96, 97, and 98. The top staff has a whole note G4 in measure 95, followed by quarter notes. The bottom staff has eighth-note patterns in measures 95 and 96, followed by quarter notes in measures 97 and 98. Dynamic markings include *f* (forte).

Duo corale

(dallo studio corale)

Diego Casadei

Bb Clar 1

Bb Clar 2

4

6

11

17

20

Two staves of music in G minor. The upper staff has rests for the first two measures, then a melodic line starting in measure 21. The lower staff has a continuous eighth-note accompaniment pattern.

23

Two staves of music in G minor. The upper staff has a melodic line with eighth notes and rests. The lower staff has a continuous eighth-note accompaniment pattern.

26

Two staves of music in G minor. The upper staff has a melodic line with eighth notes and slurs. The lower staff has a simple harmonic accompaniment.

28

Two staves of music in G minor. Both staves feature a melodic line with a rapid sixteenth-note run in measure 29, marked with a fermata.

30

Two staves of music in G minor. Both staves feature a melodic line with a rapid sixteenth-note run in measure 31, marked with a fermata.

33

Musical notation for measures 33-37. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, often beamed together, and includes some slurs. The lower staff provides a harmonic accompaniment with similar rhythmic patterns. The key signature has two flats, and the time signature is 4/4.

38

Musical notation for measures 38-41. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes. The lower staff continues the accompaniment. The notation is consistent with the previous system.

42

Musical notation for measures 42-45. The system consists of two staves. Measures 42 and 43 feature a prominent sixteenth-note scale in the upper staff, which is beamed and slurred. The lower staff has a more static accompaniment. Measures 44 and 45 return to the melodic and accompaniment patterns of the previous systems.

46

Musical notation for measures 46-53. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff has a more active melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes. The lower staff has a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and rests. The notation is consistent with the previous systems.

54

Musical notation for measures 54-57. The system consists of two staves. Measures 54 and 55 feature a prominent sixteenth-note scale in the upper staff, which is beamed and slurred. The lower staff has a more static accompaniment. Measures 56 and 57 return to the melodic and accompaniment patterns of the previous systems.